

Women Advancing Together in HPC through WHPC Student Chapters

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Abstract—In this lightning talk, we motivate the creation of a student-led chapter of the professional organization, Women in High-Performance Computing (WHPC), at one of the largest academic institutions by enrollment, Arizona State University (ASU). We believe that the strategic objectives of WHPC are best served in our community by empowering student HPC researchers with extracurricular events and leadership opportunities that increase the visibility of women in HPC, raise awareness of their underrepresentation, and provide women with opportunities to develop their social and professional networks.

Index Terms—High Performance Computing, Student Chapters, Women in HPC, Professional Societies

I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Women in High Performance Computing (WHPC) is an inclusive professional organization focused in part on increasing the participation, visibility, and professional pathways of women in the HPC workforce [1]. While the number of women in HPC continues to grow, there are still notable gaps in the representation of women. For instance, only 10% of all HPC conference publication authors in 2021 were women [2].

This representational inequity is also more broadly found in higher educational science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields, with gender gaps forming in early childhood [3]. In addition, when women choose STEM professions, they may face statistically significant unique challenges, like reduced perception and acknowledgment of achievements [4], reduced professional status [5], and unsurprisingly, increased imposter syndrome [6]. Women in STEM may also face persistence challenges prior to beginning a professional career that arise from systematic behavior [7] or, for instance, structural inadequacy, as women with no female peers are significantly less likely to finish a Ph.D. within six-years relative to those with just a few, showing that peer-composition matters [8]. Along those lines, there is evidence of a positive correlation between the share of women in a freshmen undergraduate programs and the corresponding four-year graduation rates of male peers [9]. Additional evidence shows that undergraduate students are significantly impacted by the peers they interact with

in the critical first weeks of their programs, with better outcomes for more diverse networks [10] — peer groups matter.

Relative to the broad STEM fields, HPC has intersectional challenges. For instance, there are a general lack of HPC career pathways [11]. While nascent positions like the research software engineer are becoming more prevalent in STEM [12, 13], the channels for HPC-focused careers remain opaque. Additionally, HPC is used by many disciplines yet it is not recognized as its own academic discipline [14, 15, 16], resulting in disparate communication of practice and opportunities.

This lightning talk focuses on the creation of a student-led chapter of WHPC at Arizona State University (ASU), one of the world’s largest R1 universities by enrollment [17, 18]. We believe that the strategic objectives of WHPC are best served in our community by empowering student HPC researchers with extracurricular events and leadership opportunities that increase the visibility of women in HPC, raise awareness of the underrepresentation, and provide women with opportunities to develop their social and professional networks.

ASU has its own representational gaps. From the Fall 2020 semester to Spring 2021, 92.2% of engineering technologies graduates were male and 7.8% were female [19]. Of these graduates, 55.5% were White, 32% were Hispanic or Latine, 1.6% were Asian, 0% were Black, and 10.9% were not classified. Comparatively, for the same year, 81.2% of computer and information science graduates were male and 18.8% were female [20]; of these graduates, 47.3% were White, 19.5% were Asian, 13.9% were Hispanic or Latine, 2.9% were Black, and 16.5% were not classified. These statistics reflect incongruent diversity for two advanced computing majors and limited career opportunities for the underrepresented groups.

The idea for the Women in HPC at ASU student chapter was born out of PEARC ‘24. After hearing about the WHPC Chapter at Purdue University [21], we decided that the students at ASU would greatly benefit from an analogous student chapter. With the enthusiastic support of staff and faculty within the Research Technology Office, we began drafting a constitution. Unlike most official WHPC chapters and affiliates, WHPC at ASU is

a student-led chapter. As students ourselves, we hope to provide a unique “boots on the ground” perspective to the organization and maintain a focus on students while also leveraging the experience of professionals within the ASU community.

II. STUDENT CHAPTER ORGANIZATION

HPC cannot continue to exist without the people to power it. While WHPC’s primary focus has been on career professionals, a recent WHPC blog post provided advice for students interested in a career in HPC [22]. This kind of student-focused publication is reflective of a broader student interest in HPC careers.

Students involved in student organizations gain exposure to professional societies and cultivate deeper networks with external communities [23, 24]. These clubs also provide opportunities for students to gain leadership and organizational experience. When student chapters are effective, the events they provide benefit all engaged students. For instance, one way to improve diversity and inclusion in HPC is by focusing on student outreach and engagement. In Carlana and Fort [25], the authors demonstrate that coding events, or hackathons, are an effective means to improve STEM outreach. A series of themed WHPC-at-ASU sponsored hackathons will form the backbone of our student chapter’s regular events. Themes will be chosen that reflect common pop-culture interests to make hackathons more approachable for female students that may otherwise feel intimidated by a coding event. This will also serve to distinguish WHPC at ASU from other groups, especially the male-dominated STEM student organizations. Some of the additional activities that are planned include:

- **Invited talks and panels.** At least every other regular monthly meeting will feature an invited talk or panel. These events will primarily feature local professionals, faculty, and alumni. Such events will increase the visibility of HPC role models and provide a channel for the communication of their experiences.
- **Tutorials and workshops.** In collaboration with the Research Technology Office, opportunities will be made available for members to present their HPC skills to the wider community.
- **Professional development exercises.** At least once a year, an event will be organized around professional development. Sub-events will include negotiation, pitching, public speaking, and resume workshops.
- **Lightning talks.** Opportunities will be given to members to present their research to the rest of the organization via short lightning talks. These will serve as ice breakers for the participants while also providing important exposure and public-speaking experience.

One reason women are underrepresented in HPC is due to the lack of encouragement from their parents, teachers,

and peers [26]. Engaging women and creating a safe space for them to learn will be critical to closing the HPC gender gap.

The chapter’s initial recruitment will draw from ASU’s HPC user list and through grassroots announcements in relevant classes across multiple departments. For initial introductions to broader student cohorts and engagement opportunities, specific faculty from the ASU HPC user list will be contacted for their help in meeting their students, and the ASU Research Computing Governance Board will be engaged further raise awareness. Additional collaborations will be sought from contacts in ASU’s Center for Gender Equity in Science and Technology, the ASU Women in Tech. group, and various student chapters like the Association for Women in Mathematics, Society of Women Engineers (SWE), Graduate SWE, Women in Biochemistry, and Women in Computer Sciences.

By leveraging WHPC’s established professional network, WHPC student chapters will provide a student-to-professional channel for women interested in HPC and ultimately improve career pathways.

III. CHALLENGES, GOALS, AND CONCLUSION

The largest challenges student organizations face stem from busy schedules, competing academic loyalties, and a lack of central funding. For instance, students are continuously working on their studies. Some potential WHPC at ASU members will likely not have time to commit to multiple student organizations. Also, sponsorship would improve planned events and demonstrate a real commitment from the larger community. Funding would also allow for t-shirts and other accessories, which foster a sense of belonging and camaraderie. Providing students with an incentive to join and participate in student organizations has been effective in increasing their involvement [27]. Additionally, underrepresented individuals are frequently called upon to participate in diversity, equity, and inclusion initiatives. The leaders of the student chapter must be careful not to over-commit themselves to non-chapter activities.

It is crucial to broaden the uptake and impact of advanced cyberinfrastructure [28]. This student chapter represents an effort to broaden participation from diverse communities, and many interdisciplinary allies and members are expected. We hope that by starting a WHPC student chapter on our campus, other students will be inspired to start student-led chapters on their campuses. Doing so would allow for entire student cohorts of women to advance together in HPC. This would not only lead to increased representation, but would likely lead to more professional collaborations as well.

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